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**शिक्षक - शिक्षा की भारतीय पत्रिका
अन्वेषिका**

राष्ट्रीय अध्यापक शिक्षा परिषद् (राअशिप) द्वारा प्रवर्तित शिक्षक-शिक्षा की भारतीय पत्रिका - अन्वेषिका भारत तथा भारत के बाहर आवासित अध्यापक शिक्षा के कर्णधारों को सम्बोधित है। इसका उद्देश्य शिक्षा विशेषतौर से अध्यापक शिक्षा में गुणवत्ता की चिन्ता को मुखर करना है। राअशिप जो देश में अध्यापक शिक्षा व्यवस्था के नियोजित एवं समन्वित विकास को सुकर बनाने तथा मानकों एवं मानदण्डों को सुनिश्चित करने हेतु एक शीर्षस्तरीय विधिक निकाय के रूप में गठित एवं संकल्पबद्ध है, उन नवाचारी विचारों एवं अवधारणाओं को प्रसारित करने का आधार प्रदान करती है जो शैक्षिक प्रक्रियाओं में गुणवत्ता के मुद्दों को उजागर करने में सहायक होंगी। अध्यापक शिक्षा के लिए समर्पित यह पत्रिका मूल्य-आधारित शिक्षा, सूचना एवं सम्प्रेषण प्रौद्योगिकी के उभरते नूतन आयाम जो शिक्षण-अधिगम के प्रतिमान से प्रत्यक्षतः सम्बद्ध हों, गुणवत्तापूर्ण अध्यापक शिक्षा के शाश्वत चिन्ताओं के संदर्भ में लेख, प्रतिवेदन, शोधपरक एवं अन्वेषणात्मक अध्ययनों के सारांशों की प्रस्तुति साग्रह आमंत्रित करती है।

**Indian Journal of Teacher Education
Anweshika**

The National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) has launched Indian Journal of Teacher Education - Anweshika which is addressed to Teacher Educators in India and abroad. Its intent is to promote the quality concerns in education specially in teacher education. In consonance with the vision and mandate of the NCTE as an Apex Statutory Body for facilitating planned and co-ordinated development of teacher education system in the country and for ensuring maintenance of norms and standards, it is felt imperative to disseminate innovative ideas and concepts which will strengthen the cause of quality in educational processes. Devoted as it is to teacher education, the journal invites articles, reports and summary of research and investigative studies particularly in the context of value-based education, emerging new horizons of ICT with bearing on new teaching-learning paradigms and the perennial concerns for quality teacher education.

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(Due to inadvertent reason, the past issues could not be published)

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[हिन्दी खण्ड]

उच्च शिक्षा स्तरीय शिक्षकों के प्रौद्योगिकीय प्रयोग का उनके व्यक्तिगत कारकों के सन्दर्भ में अध्ययन	छाया सोनी	67
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CONSTRUCTION AND TRYOUT OF PRE-REQUISITE TEST IN ALGEBRA OF STANDARD X

R.G. Kothari* & H.S. Mistry**

Mathematics is an important discipline of learning of the secondary stage. It predominately contributes to the development of precision, rational and analytical thinking, reasoning and scientific temper. One of the basic aims of teaching mathematics at secondary stage is to inculcate the skill of quantification of experience gathered by the learner. But still some of the students find mathematics as very difficult subject. Among different branches of mathematics, Algebra is used to enable the learner to apply its knowledge to other branches of mathematics. The pre-requisite test can help the students to know their weaknesses in the basic concepts and it also helps the teachers to know the level of their students. The authors had constructed a pre-requisite test covering all units of algebra of standard X and implemented on the randomly selected standard X students of the twelve non-granted Gujarat medium schools of Vadodara city. Based on the findings of the study, the authors discussed and suggested some ways for the teachers teaching mathematics at secondary school level.

Introduction

Mathematics as a branch of knowledge is considered as the mother of all sciences, for its fundamentals are essential to the understanding of all the concepts of science. It plays a vital role in day-to-day life. According to NPE (1986), "mathematics should be visualized as the vehicle to train a child to think, reason, analyse and to articulate logically a part from being a specific

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subject, it should be treated as a concomitant to any subject involving analysis and reasoning."

Mathematics is an important discipline of learning at the secondary stage. It predominately contributes to the development of precision, rational and analytical thinking, reasoning and scientific temper. One of the basic aims of teaching mathematics at the secondary stage is to inculcate the skill of quantification of experience gathered by the learner. But still some of the students find mathematics as very difficult subject.

Rastogi (1983) observed that "in spite of such an importance given to the subject the performance of the students in mathematics illustrates that our national performance is quite below the desirable level." National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) stated "it is in the early years, up to class IV that efforts at diagnosing and addressing remedial work in language and mathematics must be directed." The studies of Ashar (1972), Rastogi (1983) and George (2003) also show that the poor understanding mathematical concepts, lack of mastery over basic mathematical skills, lack of pre-requisites related to basic principles, fundamentals are some of the most prominent factors which hamper the students' progress in learning mathematics. According to Patel (2007), "error analysis and remedial measures also help the students to enhance their achievement to some extent."

Mathematics as a broad discipline enfolds under its umbrella subject like geometry, algebra, trigonometry, arithmetic and the like out of these, algebra is an area of study which has its application in other branches of mathematics. According to Gamoran & Hannigan (2000), "students that successfully complete Algebra rather than a general mathematics track are more likely to pursue advanced mathematics and science courses." When students make the transition from concrete arithmetic to the symbolic language of algebra, they develop abstract reasoning skills necessary to excel in mathematics and science. But the abstract reasoning skills required to solve algebraic problems develop slowly and hence students find the algebra difficult compared to arithmetic and geometry. For developing these skills an advanced training is required. For solving algebraic numerical one should be fluent in the concept of letters and symbols used to represent quantities. Formulas are a part of our lives. One has to drive a car and need to calculate the distance, or need to work out the volume of milk in a container, algebraic formulas are used every day without conscious efforts. The Calculating the price of many commodities or profit in business algebra plays a major role. Margins need to be set and calculations need to be made to do strategic planning and analyzing is the way to do it. According to Mishra (2008), "one of the main defect of the existing curriculum is, there is

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main emphasis on exercise and revision, but it is not highlighted that which part of the content should be revised." The pre-requisite test can help the students to know their weaknesses in the basic concepts and it also help the teachers to know the level of their students. On the basis of the errors committee by the students in the pre-requisite test teacher can identify the concepts which causes the low achievement of the students in mathematics. This will enable the teachers to provide remedial teaching for weak pre-requisite concepts that can enhance the learning of the new concepts. After revising the pre-requisite, the learning of new concepts of algebra at class X will definitely provide a better understanding and will also lead to higher achievement in mathematics. Therefore, the present study has been conducted by the investigators.

Review of Related Literature

Keeping in view the objectives and focus of the present study, a total of twenty one studies related to diagnosis and remediation, achievement in mathematics, achievement in algebra and pre-requisite tests in mathematics, have been reviewed.

The purpose of the studies was preparation and standardization of the test in terms to find out the weaknesses in mathematics and its reasons. The study were of Ashar (1972), Bhirud (1975), Rastogi (1983), Bhardwaj (1987), Jain & Burad (1988), Kasat (1991), George (1993), George (2003), Triwedi (2004), Patel (2004), Patel (2005) and Shah (2005), Bhardwaj (1987) and George (1993) have constructed and standardized test to find out the mathematical weaknesses and found that students were poor as far as addition and subtraction of fractions were concerned. The studies of Ashar (1972) and Bhirud (1975) were on construction and standardization of a diagnostic test in algebra. Jain & Burad (1988) and Shah (2005) have studied the difficulties in instructional process of mathematics faced by teachers and students of upper-primary class and found that the students have poor command over the basic fundamentals of mathematics subject. The studies of Rastogi (1983), Kasat (1991), George (2003), Triwedi (2004) and Patel (2005) were conducted on errors in mathematics. But only the study of Patel (2004) was conducted on the errors in Algebra. In all the reviewed studies under this category, samples were drawn from secondary schools students except the study of Shah (2005) which has selected sample from upper primary schools students. The studies found that the students are not clear when, why and how to take L.C.M. and non-availability of mathematic teachers due to late appointments and frequent teacher transfer, lack of appropriate classrooms, irregular attendance of students and insufficient periods for teaching mathematics. Ashar (1972) and Bhirud (1975) found that students committed errors due to lack of systematic approach, the errors of

conceptual type pre-dominated the computational type and trends of errors continued to a greater extent in the higher grades. The studies of Rastogi (1983), Kasat (1991), George (2003), Trivedi (2004) and Patel (2005) found that remedial programmes showed importance in terms of attitude and performance. They also found that one of the important causes of backwardness of mathematics was the poor command over basic arithmetic skills and through remedial measures command over basic arithmetic skills improved, attitude towards mathematics become more favourable and achievement increased.

All the reviewed studies related to achievement in Mathematics were survey type in nature except the experimental study of Patel (2007). The purpose of the reviewed studies was to find out the factors or attributes associated with the achievement in mathematics. All the studies were carried out on the secondary school students. Chel (1990), Nagailankin (1991) and Janet (2008) have found out the factors affecting achievement in mathematics which are attitude towards mathematics, numerical ability, abstract reasoning, gaps in knowledge of concept, difficulties in understanding of mathematical language, lack of openness and flexibility on the part of students, perceived usefulness of mathematics and motivation towards mathematics. Patel (2007) has developed a programme for enhancing achievement in mathematics and found the effectiveness of the programme through improved achievement of the student of standard.

The reviewed studies related to the achievement in Algebra, the study of Sharma (1978) was on standardization of achievement test battery whereas the purpose of the study of Little and Valerie (2008) was to measure effectiveness of vertical team teaching. Both the studies have carried out secondary students and found that imparting of limited knowledge, blind use of rules, heavy syllabus, back of natural urge, insufficient drill at primary level and absence of methodical approach of classroom teaching.

Both the studies reviewed related to pre-requisite test in Mathematics. The study of Patel (2007) has designed a series of pre-requisite tests for class X students in mathematics whereas; the study of Jayalakshmi (2010) has constructed a pre-requisite test on the basis of achievement test of standard VIII students. The major finding of the study of Patel (2007) was achievement on pre-requisite test of students was far from satisfactory and most of the students were weak in the concepts related to L.C.M., distributive laws, polynomials and items related to binomials and fractions (Jayalakshmi, 2010). Hence in the present study, the investigators tried to construct and standardize the pre-requisite test covers all the units of algebra of standard X.

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Statement of the Problem

Construction and Try-out of Pre-requisite Test in Algebra of Standard X.

Objectives of the Study

The study was carried out with a view to achieve the following objective:

1. To construct an achievement test for finding the errors committed by the students of standard X in algebra.
2. To analyse the errors committed by the students in the achievement test.
3. To construct a pre-requisite test on the basis of the analysis of the errors committed by the students in the achievement test.

Research Questions

Based on the reviewed studies, the following questions emerged which

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E.G. while solving the example: simplify $\frac{3x^5}{x^3y} + \frac{x^3y}{xy^2}$ student must have knowledge of

i) Law of indices, i.e. $\frac{x^m}{x^n} = x^{m-n}$

ii) Addition of fractions i.e. when, where and how to take L.C.M.

Delimitation of the Study

The study was delimited to the Non Grant-in-aid (NG), Gujarat medium schools of Vadodara city having secondary level following the GSHB syllabus.

METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology: The present study was quantitative in nature. It has been conducted by employing the survey method.

Population of the Study: All the Gujarat medium non-grant-in-aid secondary schools of Vadodara city constituted as a population for the present study. There were eighty nine Gujarat medium NG secondary schools in Vadodara city during the year 2011-12 (DEO Report Vadodara City, 2012). Thus, all the eighty nine Gujarat medium non-grant-in-aid secondary schools constituted population for the present study. All the students of standard X of the eighty nine non-grant-in-aid, Gujarat medium schools of Vadodara city for the academic year 2011-12 following the syllabus prescribed by GSHB were studying in standard X in all the eighty nine Gujarat medium non-grant-in-aid secondary school of Vadodara city. Thus 4895 students of standard X were formed population of the students.

Sample of the Study: For the first part of the study, out of the eighty nine NG secondary schools of Vadodara city (DEO Report of Vadodara City, 2012), two schools were selected randomly. All the students of Standard X of two selected schools were considered as a sample for the achievement test. During the administration of the achievement test, there were ninety students presented in both the NG Gujarat medium schools so the sample size was ninety students for the first part of the study. For the second part of the study, out of remaining eighty seven non-grant-in-aid secondary schools of Vadodara city, twelve schools were selected randomly by lottery method. All the students of standard X of twelve selected schools were the sample for the present study. Thus, cluster sampling technique was used in selecting sample. The size of the sample of the

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standard X students was 600. Table 1 presents school wise sample size taken under the present investigation.

Table 1: School wise Sample Size of the Students

Sr. No. No.	SVS	Name of the secondary School	Total No. of Students
1.	5	New Heaven Vidyalaya, Waghodiya Road	44
2.		Swami Vivekanad Vidyalaya, Parivar Char Rasta	55
3.		Shreyas Vidyalaya, Pologround	49
4.	6	Utkarsh Vidyalaya, Harinagar	52
5.		Rameshwar Vidyalaya, Gotri Road	47
6.		Saurabh Vidyalaya, Old Padra Road	51
7.	7	Shree Krishna Vidyalaya, Kerelibaug	52
8.		Ambe School, Manjulpur	45
9.		Shantiniketan Vidyalaya, Maneja	49
10.	8	Shree T.R. Patel Vidyalaya, Nizampura	53
11.		Ambe Vidyalaya, Sama	48
12.		Urmi School, Sama	50
Grand Total			600

Tools for Data Collection

Achievement Test: The Achievement test was constructed for the chapters of Linear equation in two variables, H.C.F and L.C.M. of Polynomials, Quadratic Equations and Rational Expression. The purpose of the test was to find out the errors committed by the students in four chapters of algebra, to identify the concepts in which students were facing the problem and to identify the pre-requisites of algebra possessed by the students. No marks were assigned to the test items as the purpose is only to identify the efforts.

Pre-requisite Text

Step I: Preparation of the Items for the Pre-requisite Test : Items for

the pre-requisite test were designed based on errors committed by the students in the achievement test. Also the opinions of Mathematics teachers of secondary schools were considered for designing the items. Furthermore, few answer books of students also examined to find the nature of the errors committed by the students. For each prerequisite minimum one item was prepared and hence total fifty items were prepared in the initial tool. The investigator carried out the content analysis of each item for the pre-requisite test and the learning outcomes were decided. The Table 2 shows content analysis, learning outcomes and no. of items selected.

Table 2: Content analysis of Pre-requisite Test, learning outcomes and items

Sr. No.	Content analysis	Learning outcomes	No. of items
1.	Factorization in quadratic equation	1. Student will be to factorize of quadratic equations.	
		2. Students will be able to find out the last term of quadratic equation.	3
		3. Students will be able to recall the formula of multiplication of factors	
2.	Solution of Linear equation in two variables.	Students will be able to solve linear equation in two variables.	2
3.	Simplification of the equation and find the value of variable x	Students will be able to simplify the equation to find the solution of variable x	1
4.	Graph of Equation	Students will be able to solve the equation to plot the points on graph	2
5.	Linear equation in two variables	Students will be able to identify the linear equation in two variables.	1
6.	Concept of expansion	Students will be able to expand the equation to find last item.	1
7.	Simplification of expansion	1. Students will be able to factorize its expansion simplification for solution 2. Students will be able to simplify the multiplication of two factors for solution	4

(Contd. Table in next page)

total 50 items were removed. Hence 12 + 5 = 17 items were left under the experts of exper

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Sr. No.	Content analysis	Learning outcomes	No. of Items
8.	Factorization of Polynomial	Students will be able to factorize its expansion with simplification for solution.	2
9.	Value of expression	Students will be able to find the value of expression with the help of expansion formula	2
10.	Solution of the equation by using the method of	Students will be able to solve systems of equations using the method of elimination	4
11.	Use of Expansion formula for simplification	Students will be able to simplify and find the value of expression with the help of expansion formula	1
12.	Polynomial and square root	Students will be able to identify the expression which are square root of polynomials in or not	1
13.	Addition of Polynomial	Students will be able to solve addition of two polynomials.	1
14.	Subtraction of Polynomial	Students will be able to solve subtraction of two polynomials.	1
15.	Division of Polynomial	Students will be able to solve division of two polynomials.	1
16.	Finding the last term in polynomial	Students will be able to find last term of polynomials for making polynomial in square root.	1

Step II: Validation of Pre-requisite Test : The test was validated by two experts in the field of education and four teachers having more than five years of experience in teaching of mathematics in standard X, the purpose of validation of the tool was to know whether students really commit errors in the concepts under the test. The experts found the test little length. The experts suggested that two separate items could be merged to decrease the number of the test items e.g. one of the concepts was addition and subtraction of fraction and two items were selected for these concepts i.e.

(i) $\frac{5}{12} + \frac{4}{15} + \frac{1}{16}$ and (ii) $\frac{19}{5} - \frac{11}{6}$. These two items were replaced by $\frac{5}{6} + \frac{4}{7} - \frac{11}{2}$. Hence by incorporating the suggestions of the experts twenty items were removed from the initial draft of the pre-requisite test and total thirty items of total 50 marks were taken in the final draft of the pre-requisite test.

d. Table in next page)

Data Collection : The test was administered on ninety students of standard X which was not the part of the sample for the study. Before administration of the achievement test the investigator confirmed that four chapters have been taught in the selected schools.

For administering the pre-requisite test, permission was taken from the principals of twelve selected secondary schools. After taking permission from the selected school principals, time schedule for the data collection have been decided and the pre-requisite test was administered as per the time and date given by the respective school teachers. From all the ten selected secondary schools of Vadodara city, pre-requisite test was administered on the total of 600 students. Investigators had supervised the class when the test was going on. Total twelve days were spent for collecting the data from twelve schools i.e. one-day for one school. Students were not informed about the administration of the pre-requisite test. Before the administration of the pre-requisite test, students were given necessary instructions and ensured that the result of this test will not affect their final results.

Data Analysis

Analysis of Achievement Test : The analysis and interpretation of each item of achievement test was done and based on that few basic concepts were identified in which students faced difficulty. Item wise error analysis sheet was prepared to find out the percentage of the students committing errors in each item of achievement tests.

Analysis of Pre-requisite Test : In the analysis of pre-requisite test, the error analysis sheet was prepared in terms to find out item-wise frequency and percentage of the errors committed by the students in the particular basic concepts which were considered as pre-requisites. Mean, median, mode and standard Deviation of the obtained scores were also calculated.

Major Findings of the Study

Findings of Achievement Test

- 48.15 percent of the students could not solve the systems of equations using the method of elimination due to lack of understanding to put given values in place of 'a' and 'b' for elimination of variables. Also could not identify the coefficient from the given equation.
- 23 percent of the students could not solve the systems of equations by the

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method of cross-multiplication due to Lack of understanding to use Cramer's rule for solving equation, unable to transform the term from L.H.S. to R.H.S. or vice versa and committed errors in cross multiplication. Also an error occurs while dividing binomial with binomial and misunderstanding about the law of distribution in multiplication. 19 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

- 18.52 percent of the students could not solve the problems by using equation due to errors in the formula of Perimeter of rectangle and area of rectangle and also could not simplify the equation of the form $ax+b=c$ whereas, 24.07 percent of the students could not attempt the question.
- Eighteen percent of the students could not solve the problems by using equation due to unable to convert geometrical formulates into simple formulates for assumption, could not use triangles formula for simplification such as $m\angle A + m\angle B + m\angle C = 180$.
- Nearly 43 percent of the students could not find H.C.F. of the polynomials due to errors in factorization of second degree polynomial of the form ax^2+bx+c , unable to expand the middle term of the polynomial, unable to take the common term after factorization, misunderstanding about the factorization of the factors in the form of a^3+b^3 and errors to find the factor by using remainder theorem.
- 46 percent of the students could not find L.C.M. of the polynomials due to errors in factorization of the perfect square and perfect cube, unable to find the least common factors of the polynomials after factorization. Committed errors in factorization of the degree polynomial of the form ax^2+bx+c and differentiation of two squares.
- 63.50 percent of the students could not find L.C.M. of the polynomials due to errors in taking the common term especially when the term is negative, Made errors in the law of natural indices and committed errors to find out the square roots and division of monomial by monomial. 20.63 percent of the student could not attempt the question.
- 31.75 percent of the students could not find the value of variables, while given H.C.F. of the polynomials due to misunderstanding about addition of two negative integers, unable to use the given H.C.F. for find out the value of a and b by putting the values in polynomials $p(x)$ and $q(x)$, lack of understanding to factorize the given polynomial and errors to find out the value of k from the polynomials. 30.16 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

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- 53.52 percent of the students committed errors to inverse rational expression of the opposite expression and vice versa due to lack of clarity of inverse and opposite term. They confused and mixed both the concepts. 26.76 percent of the students could not attempt the question.
- 74.65 percent of the students could not find the value of variable from the polynomial expression due to lack of knowledge of cube and while dividing the positive integer with negative integer. The made sign erros.
- 48 percent of the students could not attempt the question of simplify polynomial expression whereas, 46 percent of the students could not simplify polynomial expression while multiplication, division and addition operation used due to lack of understanding of the multiplication and division of polynomials. They made errors in the simple multiplication of integers, Lack of knowledge of factors of perfect cubè binomial and inability of simplify.
- Nearly 34 percent of the students could not check the equation as quadratic

The value of mean, median and mode were 36.42, 37.5 and 37 respectively which indicates that the pre-requisites possessed by the students are not normally distributed around the selected sample of students.

Findings of Pre-requisite Text

71.70 percent of the students could not find the value of k , when equation of the form ax^2+bx+c due to take LCM of fraction, to multiply integer with fraction and to square the fraction whereas, 24.52 percent of the students could not attempt the question. 13.21 percent of the students could not give correct answer due to lack of understanding of the addition of positive and negative integers, lack of understanding of division of positive and negative integers, lack of clarity in the concept of square and square root, unable to solve the equation of $ax+b=c$; $a \neq 0$ whereas, 24.52 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

15.10 percent of the students could not find the value of k , when equation of the form ax^2+bx+c and discriminant D is given due to transform the term from LHS to RHS and this was the reason for their sign errors and lack of clarity of addition of two like terms whereas, 24.52 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

23.5 percent of the students could not find the discriminant D due to lack of concept clarity of square and square root, lack of understanding about the concept of coefficient of quadratic equation and sign error in multiplication of two negative integers whereas, 25.5 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

33 percent of the students could not be able to multiply rational number with irrational number, could not simplify the equation of the form $ax^2+bx+c=0$, lack of concept clarity of coefficient and the square of negative integer is a negative integer whereas, 14 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

angle triangle and Pythagoras Rule, lack of understanding the multiplication of monomial with binomial, unable to cover the mathematical statement into the symbolic form, lack of concept clarity of reciprocal, lack of concept clarity of square and square root, lack of understanding to use Pythagoras Theorem, lack of clarity of the calculation of loss, inability to transform the term from LHS to RHS and that is why they committed sign errors, unable to factorize the polynomial of the form ax^2+bx+c . 45 percent of the students could not attempt the question.

- The value of Standard deviation was 6.3884, which indicates that achievement in pre-requisite test has more variation i.e. the group of students is heterogeneous regarding the required knowledge of pre-requisites.
- Skewness was -1.281, which indicates that distribution is negatively skewed. Negatively skewed indicating that scores are massed at the right hand of the scale, scores are spread gradually towards the left hand. But in this case distribution seems to be non-normal, because all the scores are not spread ultimately towards left-hand.
- 67 percent of the students committed errors in factorization of the polynomial due to lack of concept clarity of factorization and its expansion with simplification.
- 58 percent of the students committed errors to find solution of linear equation in two variables due to lack of simplification and unable to convert and find the value of variable 'x' or 'y', while twenty percent of the students could not attempt the equation for answer.
- 51 percent of students committed errors to simplify an expansion for solution due to lack of concept clarity of factorization and its expansion with simplification, unable to use the expansion of $(x+y)^2 = x^2+2xy+y^2$, $(x-y)^2 = x^2-2xy+y^2$ for simplification.
- 48 percent students could not solve the equations by using the method of elimination due to Lack to understanding of the solution of the equation of the form $ax+by=c$; $a, b \neq 0$, unable to transform the term from LHS to RHS and vice versa to find the value of variable x and y. while 36 students could not attempt question for answer.
- 35 percent students could not fill the blank of linear equation in two variables due to false identification of linear equation in two variables, lack of concept clarity about the Linear equation in two variables and its main equation $ax+by+c=0$.
- Around 37 percent students could not fill the blank of Graph of equation for parallel line due to decide that which equation is parallel line to Y axis, unable to plot the points on the co-ordinate plane and not in a position to draw a parallel line to Y axis.

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29 percent students could not factorize the polynomial due to lack of concept clarity of factorization and its expansion with simplification. Do not know the formula of factorization, i.e. $a^2-b^2 = (a+b)(a-b)$, and lack of concept clarity about the factorization and its main equation $(x-y)^2 = x^2-2xy+y^2$.

Nearly 38 percent of the students could not simplify the expression to find solution due to lack of concept clarity of factorization and its expansion with simplification, unable to simplify the multiplication of two factors, unable to calculate after multiplication of two factors.

17 percent of the students could not factorize the polynomial to find the last term of the polynomial due to lack of concept clarity of factorization of quadratic equation, do not know to use the formula for finding last term of quadratic equation, unable to simplify the factors multiplication to find one solution in the form of equation.

25 percent of the students could not simplify the factors into expansion form due to lack of concept clarity of factorization and its expansion with simplification, unable to simplify the multiplication of two factors, unable to calculate after multiplication of two factors, Unable to use the expansion of $(x+y)^2 = x^2+2xy+y^2$, $(x-y)^2 = x^2-2xy+y^2$ for simplification.

Around 38 percent of the students could not solve the equation by using the method of elimination due to lack of understanding of the solution of the equation of the form $ax+by=c$; $a, b \neq 0$, unable to transform the term from LHS to RHS and vice versa to find the value of variable x and y .

31 percent of the students could not find the value of $x^2 = \frac{x^2}{1}$, If $x \frac{x}{1} = 2$ given due to errors in squaring both the side of $x + \frac{x}{1} = 2$, unable to solve the expansion after squaring of $x + \frac{x}{1} = 2$.

28 percent of the student could not decide the polynomial is square-root or not due to lack of concept clarity of Polynomial and its square root.

21 percent students could not add two polynomials due to lack of concept clarity of addition of polynomials, unable to identify like terms and unlike terms in polynomials and unable to add like terms and dislike terms for finding the last solution.

25 percent of the students could not subtract one polynomial from other due to lack of concept clarity of subtraction of polynomials, unable to identify

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like terms and unlike terms in polynomials and unable to subtract like terms and dislike terms for finding the last solution.

Discussion

Understanding Mathematics is an important part of understanding our world. The subject and its applications in Science, Commerce and Technology are important. Its important role can be ensured if students understand and appreciate the relationships and patterns of both number and space in their daily life. Mathematics is a subject in which learning of every new concept is based upon the basic concept which is learnt before. The present study focused on the errors committed by the students in the basic concepts of mathematics, which are necessary to be possessed by the students for learning a new concept in mathematics. Out of the four branches of mathematics algebra is found difficult to learn by most of the students. Bhardwaj (1987) also came out with 50.6 percent error rate in the area of algebra. The learning of algebra also includes the learning of basic arithmetic skills. The weak commands over basic arithmetic skills affect their achievement in mathematics. Rastogi (1983) found that one of the important causes of backwardness of mathematics was the poor command over basic arithmetic skills.

In the present study, the investigators constructed the pre-requisite test on the basis of the errors committed by the students in the achievement test of four chapters of Algebra of standard X Mathematics. The pre-requisite test included the items related to the basic concepts which are required to be possessed by the students. By analyzing the errors committed by the students in pre-requisite test, the investigators came up with certain major findings. It was found that most of the students committed errors in the item related to the concept of coefficient which the students learned at standard VI, the laws of natural indices which the students learned at VIII. The students committed sign errors in these concepts. This finding also supports the findings that the students were poor with regard to signs and indices comparing of fractions with negative signs (George, 1993 and Trivedi, 2004). Patel (2007) also found that the students could not find values of powers and indices due to insufficient knowledge. It is found that the students were weak in the concept of L.C.M. Shah (2005), Patel (2007) and Jayalakshmi (2010) also found that the students were not clear and how to take L.C.M. and they could not find L.C.M. of algebraic expression due to lack of clarity between H.C.F. and L.C.M. It is found that most of the students committed errors in factorization and expansion which they learned at standard VIII. Patel (2007) also found that the students were unable to solve examples related to factors expansion. Trivedi (2004) also found that the students were not able to apply formulas for factorization. It is found that the students could

not solve the equations of the form $ax+b=c$; $a \neq 0$ and $ax+by=a$; $a, b \neq 0$. George (2003) also found that the students could not solve the linear equations even fill in the blanks. It is found that the students could not simplify by opening bracket and they committed sign errors in that. Trivedi (2004) also found that the students were weak in addition and subtraction specially while opening the brackets. It is found that the students were committed errors in the items related to the concepts like Multiplication of two binomials, division of monomial by monomial and division of binomial with binomial. Jaylaxshmi (2010) also found more incorrect responses for the items related to monomial, binomial and polynomial.

Based on the discussion, the investigators conclude that the students committed errors due to their lack of clarity in the basic concepts and insufficient knowledge regarding the basic concepts. So the reflection upon those basic concepts before teaching new concepts is required to revise with reflective overview. The constructed pre-requisite test will help the teacher to identify the basic concepts where students commit errors and which needs reflection upon them. Effective teaching requires that common errors and misconceptions are systematically confronted and explored within the classroom. Hence, it is important to select a variety of experiences and examples with concrete materials to represent the concept adequately. Each new concept makes Mathematics come alive for the children. This kind of teaching makes children active participants in the learning process. Through the touching and moving objects, the involvement of multiple senses tends to make the learning more permanent. In this way learning becomes an active process of building knowledge and making sense. This will help the teacher to minimize the errors of the students and enhance the achievement of the student at some extent.

Suggestion for the Teachers

- Teacher should identify the complex concept in Mathematics and try to frame lesson plan on the basis of simple to complex approach.
- Teacher should identify the weakness of your students towards concept formation based on the unit test, classroom questioning, checking note books, drill & practice in classroom and homework checking.
- Teacher should conduct pre-requisite tests for all the chapters of Mathematics of standard X.
- Teacher should conduct unit wise diagnosis and remedial programme based on the evaluation.

- Teacher should identify the pre-requisite for each unit and provide remedial measures accordingly.
- A small group-teaching, peer group teaching strategy should be worked out for the weak students.

Suggestion for Further Study

- Similar study can be conducted for other topics of class V to XII also.
- A Study of achievement and pre-requisite can be conducted with various variables like socio economic status of the students, parents' qualification and students' attitude towards Mathematics.
- A case study for low achiever students in Algebra of secondary school Mathematics can be conducted.
- A case study for high achiever students in Algebra of secondary school Mathematics can be conducted.
- Factors affecting pre-requisite also can be studies.

References

- Ashar, R.R. (1972). Construction and Standardization of the Diagnostic Test in Basic Algebraic Skills for the Pupils of Gujarati Medium Secondary Schools of Greater Bombay. (An unpublished Ph.D. thesis). In M.B. Buch (Ed.), *Second Survey of Research in Education*. Baroda: Society for Education Research and Development.
- Bhardwaj, R.P. (1987). Standardization of a Comprehensive Diagnostics test and Preparation of Remedial Material in Mathematics for Middle Standard of Haryana (An Unpublished Ph.D. Edu., Kurukshetra University). In M.B. Buch (Ed.), *Fourth Survey of Research in Education*. NCERT: New Delhi.
- Bhirud, G. (1975). Construction and Standardization of a Diagnostic Test in Algebra. (An unpublished Ph.D. Edu., Poona University). In M.B. Buch (Ed.), *Second Survey of Research in Education*. Baroda: Society for Education Research and Development.
- Chief., M. (1990). Diagnosis and Remediation of Underachievement in Compulsory Mathematics of Secondary Examination in West-Bengal. (An Unpublished Ph.D. Edu., University of Calcutta). In A.K. Sharma (Ed.), *Fifth Survey of Research in Education*. NCERT: New Delhi.
- DEO Report of Vadodara city (2012). *List of schools of Vadodara city*. Retrieved on February 2, 2012 from <http://www.deovadodara.gov.in>.
- Gamoran, A. & Hannigan, E. (200). Algebra for everyone? Benefits of College Preparatory Mathematics for Students with Diverse Abilities in Early Secondary School. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*. 22 (3), 241-254.

Students in Upper Primary Class. An Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda. Vadodara.

Sharma, A.K. (1978). A Critical Study of Achievement in Mathematics by Pupils of Secondary Schools with Particular reference to the State of Assam. (An Unpublished PhD. Thesis, Education, Gauhati University). In M.B. Buch (Ed.), *Third Survey of Research in Education*. NCERT: New Delhi.

Trivedi, K. (2004). *A Study of Errors committed in Algebra by Class VIII Students in Vadodara City*. An Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation (Education), The Maharaja Sayajirao University Baroda, Vadodara.

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